

Jute Seeds—*Corchorus Capsularis*. Part III. Their Chemical Composition.

BY NIRMAL KUMAR SEN.

In a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 759) an account was given of the composition of jute seed oil. It appeared, however, of importance and interest to extend the investigation by examining also the other constituents of the seeds.

The first chemical investigation of the seeds of *Corchorus capsularis* was by Tsuno (*Monatsh. pr. Tierheilkunde*, 1895, 6, 455), who indicated the presence of a bitter principle under the name of *corchorin*. The corchorin of Tsuno was a brown amorphous powder and turned bluish-green with concentrated sulphuric acid. But the glucoside obtained from the seeds of the same plant by the present author seemed to be different from corchorin as it was a white crystalline substance and developed a red colouration with sulphuric acid.

From all the data that are available regarding Tsuno's corchorin it appears that after all it was a highly impure specimen, from which no attempt was made to prepare any substance in a pure and crystalline condition. It may be mentioned here incidentally that a substance answering all the descriptions of Tsuno's corchorin was first obtained during the preliminary process of isolation of the bitter principle from the seeds of *Corchorus capsularis*. But on investigation, this product was subsequently resolved into a number of components amongst which a crystalline glucoside having an intensely bitter taste was found to be the essential principle. Contrary to the assertion of the previous investigators, this substance was found to be free from nitrogen and so it could not be an alkaloid as they had supposed.

Another pharmacological investigation relating to *Corchorus capsularis* has furthermore been recorded by Kobert (*Ber. Natur. Ges. Rostock; Arch. Freund Natur. Ges. Mecklenburg*, 1906, No. 5; vide *Chem. Zentr.*, 1907, 1, 1273) who had received the impure product from the firm of Merck for his experiment on animals. In this connection he described certain chemical and physical properties

of the substance. But none of the workers made any statement regarding the isolation and purification of the bitter principle and there was no mention of its melting point and composition.

A still later publication embraces a study of *Corchorus capsularis* by Annett (*Biochem. J.*, 1917, 11, 192) in which he stated that the seeds contained raffinose to the extent of about 2.25 per cent. but he made no statement concerning the other constituents of the seeds.

From the brief review of the literature it will be observed that no complete chemical examination has hitherto been made of jute seeds and nothing is known about the composition of the bitter principle which was considered to be the probable source of the reputed physiological action of the seeds which are used to some extent medicinally in India.

The bitter principle of jute seeds isolated by the present author was found to be a colourless substance crystallising in stout rhombic prisms, m. p. 174-175°. It had a molecular formula of $C_{22}H_{36}O_8$ and possessed an intensely bitter taste. Its character as a glucoside was proved by the fact that on hydrolysis by mineral acids it lost a molecule of glucose and was converted into another substance of alcoholic character.

Saha and Chowdhury (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1044) described a compound under the name of *capsularin* which they obtained from the leaves of the same plant having the same molecular formula and melting point as the corchorin isolated by the present author from the seeds of the same plant. But the most interesting thing about corchorin is that it is dextrorotatory $[\alpha]_D = +33.4$, whereas capsularin is levorotatory $[\alpha]_D = -23.6$. The former is insoluble in dilute mineral acids and is resinified when heated with 2% sulphuric acid without being hydrolysed whereas the latter dissolves and is easily hydrolysed when heated with 2% sulphuric acid.

Though there appears to be little doubt that these compounds are closely related, the connection between them cannot be predicted with any reasonable certainty until sufficient data regarding their composition are forthcoming.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The material employed for this investigation was obtained through the kindness of Prof. J. C. Ghosh, D.Sc., who had specially procured a quantity of the seeds for the author from Mr. R. S. Fin-

low, Director of Agriculture, Bengal. The author had thus the assurance that the material was perfectly authentic.

Test for Alkaloid.—A portion of the crushed seeds (10 g.) when treated with Prollius fluid (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1882, 19, 85) did not give any reaction for alkaloid.

Fermentation of the Seeds.—The seeds on soaking in water quickly began to ferment with evolution of gas. Preliminary examination showed that hydrogen and carbon dioxide were produced.

No fermentation of the seeds took place when they were treated with 2 per cent. copper sulphate solution and immersed in sterile water for a fortnight, nor when thymol was added to a mass of crushed seeds and water. The fermentation was therefore, due to bacteria.

Test for Enzyme.—A quantity (100 g.) of the ground seeds was macerated with distilled water at the ordinary temperature for three days with the addition of a little chloroform to prevent bacterial action. To the filtrate about three times its volume of 95 per cent. alcohol was added, when an abundant pale brown flocculent precipitate was produced. After standing for some time the precipitate was collected, washed successively with a little alcohol, ether and dried in *vacuo* over sulphuric acid. When dry it formed a brown mass which could be triturated to a grayish powder and amounted to 3.4 per cent. of the weight of the seeds employed.

The freshly prepared substance was at first capable of re-resolution in water. Its aqueous solution was slightly turbid and did not give any colouration with ferric chloride but gave a flocculent white precipitate insoluble in acetic acid with lead acetate. It contained nitrogen and an acidified solution of the substance gave a white precipitate with potassium mercuric iodide. It did not hydrolyse amygdaline but when a little quantity of the substance was placed in a test tube and covered with a dilute solution of hydrogen peroxide a brisk evolution of oxygen took place thus indicating the presence of catalase.

Table I gives the proximate analysis of the seeds and Table II that of the ash.

TABLE I.

Moisture	...	7.1%	Crude fibre	...	20.76%
Ash	...	6.0%	Free invert sugar	...	3.079%
Protein (N. 6.25)	26.62%		Sugar by inversion	...	5.95%
	Starch trace.				

TABLE II.

Ash soluble in water	... 24.5%	P ₂ O ₅	... 39.16%
Ash soluble in acid	... 74.2%	SiO ₂ as sand	... 1.30%
Sand and silicate (by difference).	... 1.8%	Fe ₂ O ₃	Traces, not estimated.
	TOTAL ... 100.00	MgO	... 8.21%
Alkalinity of the ash (in terms of K ₂ CO ₃).	... 9.25%	CaO	... 20.73%
		Al ₂ O ₃	Not estimated.
		Na ₂ O	... 3.23%
		K ₂ O	... 25.45%
		SO ₂	... 4.24%
		CO ₂	Not estimated.
		Cl ₂	Traces, not estimated.
		TOTAL	96.32%

Extraction with various solvents.—In order to ascertain the general character of the constituents, 50 gm. of the powdered seeds were extracted successively in a Soxhlet's apparatus with various solvents whereby the following amounts of extract, dried at 100° were obtained.

Petroleum ether (b. p. 40-60°) extracted	14.72%
Ether	1.36%
Chloroform	1.9%
Alcohol (95%)	15.72%
Water	7.1%
Residue	56.00%
Loss	3.2%
TOTAL	100.00

Petroleum extract.—This extract contained a fatty oil—a detailed account of which had been given in Part II (*loc. cit.*).

Ether extract.—The extract, after the complete removal of the solvent, was a yellowish green viscous mass. It was re-dissolved in a large volume of cold ether whereby a small quantity of sparingly soluble substance was obtained.

The more readily soluble extract was a greenish viscous mass and was shaken up repeatedly first with an aqueous solution of sodium carbonate and then with dilute solution of caustic soda. The combined extracts were then extracted in acid solution with low boiling naphtha (90-50°). The small amount of nearly colourless fatty acid thus isolated was crystallised from alcohol and possessed the following constants: m. p. 30-32°; neutralisation value 181.5; mean molecular weight 309.1 and iodine value 54.6 (Hubl's).

The ethereal solution, which had been extracted with aqueous sodium carbonate, was washed, dried and the solvent removed, when a small quantity of fatty oil was obtained, which would naturally be expected to be similar in composition to that obtained from the seeds by extracting with light petroleum ether. It was found to contain a very small quantity of sterols melting at 126.5-128°. The mixed fatty acids obtained on hydrolysis contained, like those obtained from the extracted oil, mixture of oleic, linoleic, palmitic, and stearic acids.

The sparingly soluble substance of the ether extract of the seeds was a crystalline brittle powder—the greater portion of it was found in the flask during the extraction of the seeds with ether. When purified from alcohol (animal charcoal) it was obtained as a white micro-crystalline powder, insoluble in water but soluble in warm 90 per cent. alcohol. It dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with a violet colour and its alcoholic solution gave a green colouration with ferric chloride and a white precipitate with alcoholic lead acetate solution. It was tasteless and did not contain nitrogen. On account of the very small amount of the material it could not be further investigated.

Chloroform extract.—This extract was a brown viscous mass from which no crystalline product could be isolated.

Alcoholic extract.—The residue from the chloroform extract of the seeds (a lot of 2.8 kilograms) was completely extracted with hot 95 per cent. alcohol in a Soxhlet's apparatus. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and allowed to stand. After a time lumps of crystalline mass (73 gm.) separated; these were collected, dissolved in warm water and filtered from oily and colouring matter. The filtrate was evaporated to a syrup under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in 90 per cent. boiling alcohol (animal charcoal), filtered and allowed to stand. On the following day glistening stout prismatic needles arranged in hemispherical masses

separated out which melted at 72-74°. It was very soluble in hot water and had a slightly sweet taste and did not reduce Fehling's solution. The substance, on hydrolysis with mineral acids readily reduced Fehling's solution. When heated in a dry test-tube it lost water of crystallisation and at 120° turned brownish yellow and its solution then reduced Fehling's solution. It gave Salivanoff's reaction and on boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid gave a red-dish-brown colouration.

The substance was dried in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid at the ordinary temperature for 16 days during which about 14.22 per cent. of water was lost and the constant weight was obtained after 27 days when it lost 14.24 per cent. of water. The last trace of water of crystallisation was removed by drying it in *vacuo* in a toluene-bath in presence of phosphorus pentoxide and it showed to contain 14.94 per cent. water of crystallisation. It was dextrorotatory $[\alpha]_D = +109.3^\circ$ and the molecular weight of the substance by the cryoscopic method was found to be 635.

Hydrolysis of the sugar.—5 Gm. of the substance were hydrolysed by heating with 3 per cent. sulphuric acid. It was then neutralised with barium carbonate and filtered. One half of the filtrate when heated with an alcoholic solution of *o*-methylphenylhydrazine yielded *d*-galctosemethylphenylhydrazone, m.p. 180°.

The other half of the hydrolysed product when slowly oxidised with nitric acid (sp. gr. 1.15) at 60° yielded mucic acid.

A portion of the neutral hydrolysed product gave a beautiful blue colouration with a saturated aqueous solution of ammonium molybdate in three minutes at 40°—thus indicating the presence of fructose in the hydrolysed product (Pinoff's test for fructose in presence of other sugars, *Chem. Ztg.*, 1914, 38, 629).

It is evident from the above results that raffinose is present in the seeds of *Corchorus capsularis* and this observation is quite in accordance with that of Annett (*loc. cit.*) who obtained raffinose from jute seeds by precipitating it with ether from the alcoholic extract of the seeds.

On further standing, the alcoholic mother-liquor from which raffinose had been removed deposited a green mass. This was filtered and the residue was well washed with dilute alcohol. The slimy green residue was successively extracted with petroleum ether, ether and alcohol (90 per cent.). The alcoholic solution yielded a green soft waxy mass. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in

yellowish brown microscopic needles, m.p. 95-98° with decomposition. It was soluble in hot alcohol with a light green fluorescence, sparingly soluble in ether, insoluble in water, alkali and sodium bicarbonate solutions. It gave a beautiful violet colouration with ferric chloride and a white precipitate with lead acetate in alcoholic solution. It did not decolourise bromine. When heated on platinum foil it first melted and then burnt with a smoky flame without leaving any residue. It was tasteless and did not contain nitrogen. (Found: C, 68.83; H, 12.53. $C_{10}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 68.96; H, 12.64 per cent.). There was not sufficient substance left to determine its molecular weight and further work is in progress.

Isolation of Oorchorin.—The alcoholic filtrate after the removal of the solvent under reduced pressure yielded a thin dark brown viscous mass. This was mixed with water and subjected to distillation with steam until volatile matters ceased to pass over. A distillate was obtained which contained some white solid substance floating on the surface. The distillate was neutral to litmus and about two litres were collected. It was saturated with sodium chloride and extracted with ether, the ethereal solution being washed with water, dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. There was thus obtained a very small quantity (0.065 g.) of brownish semi-solid mass having a smoky odour. It did not give any colouration with ferric chloride. The amount was too small for further investigation.

After the removal of the volatile matter there remained in the distilling flask an aqueous liquid (A) and a small quantity of black resin (B).

As the greater portion of the resin (B) contained in the aqueous liquid was in too fine a state of division to admit of its separation by filtration, this was partially effected by decantation and it was subsequently well washed with water. The aqueous liquid which still possessed a milky appearance was treated with an excess of 10 per cent. solution of lead acetate, which produced a voluminous yellowish precipitate. This was collected on a filter, thoroughly washed with water, suspended in water and decomposed by hydrogen sulphide. On filtering the mixture a red liquid was obtained. The liquid was concentrated under reduced pressure and as it gave nothing crystalline on standing, was finally mixed with purified powdered pumice stone and successively extracted in a Soxhlet's appa-

ratu with ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate and alcohol. These solvents, however, did not effect the separation of any crystalline substance.

The filtrate from the lead acetate precipitate was treated with sulphuretted hydrogen for the removal of the excess of lead, filtered and the excess of sulphuretted hydrogen was removed in a current of carbon dioxide. The yellow sparkling filtrate was extremely bitter and contained a large amount of sugar since it readily reduced Fehling's solution and yielded an osazone, m.p. 202°.

The liquid, however, on standing deposited slowly a white sandy micro-crystalline powder having an extremely bitter taste. It was afterwards found that the filtrate on concentration and exposure to air for a few days yielded the same crystals. It was filtered, washed successively with water, absolute alcohol and ether and finally dried in *vacuo* over sulphuric acid. The yield was about 0.4 per cent. of the weight of the dry seeds.

After crystallisation from alcohol (animal charcoal) it was obtained in the form of colourless rhombic prisms, m.p. 174-175° and from dilute pyridine, after a week, in short prisms with rounded ends melting at the same temperature. It was sparingly soluble in water and chloroform, insoluble in ether but readily soluble in alcohol (95 per cent.). It dissolved in cold concentrated sulphuric acid with a red colour with green fluorescence and decolourised bromine in acetic acid solution in the cold. It was readily soluble in pyridine and acetic acid but insoluble in benzene. Its aqueous solution was neutral to litmus and was extremely bitter. The bitterness of the substance was so intense that it could be detected in 5 c.c. of water to which 0.1 c.c. of an one per cent. alcoholic solution of the substance had been added. A smaller quantity could not be detected by the bitter taste. The bitterness could be removed by shaking the aqueous solution several times with freshly ignited animal charcoal. By extracting the dried charcoal thus treated with hot absolute alcohol the bitter constituent could be recovered. It reduced ammoniacal silver nitrate in alcoholic solution but not Fehling's solution and turned potassium ferricyanide solution containing a little ferric chloride blue (Turnbull's blue). On warming with moderately strong mineral acids a light yellow solid separated out and the filtrate, after neutralisation, reduced Fehling's solution on warming. The mixture after hydrolysis gave a fatty smell. The bitter could be salted out from a concentrated aqueous

solution by ammonium sulphate and was precipitated by tannic acid and basic lead acetate. By digesting the tannate of the glucoside with zinc oxide and extracting the mixture with alcohol, the bitter could be obtained in the alcoholic solution.

On heating the substance in an air oven for 24 hours at 110-112° it did not lose any weight thus indicating the absence of water of crystallisation in the substance. In a very finely divided condition it attacked the mucous membrane of the nose and produced violent sneezing. In alcoholic or aqueous solution it did not give any colouration with ferric chloride nor any precipitate with either copper acetate, lead acetate or silver nitrate. But when a little of the substance was dissolved in chloroform with acetic anhydride and a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid subsequently added a blue colouration was produced which readily changed to green. It did not contain nitrogen. On heating on a platinum foil it first melted to a yellow liquid, charred and then completely burnt with a yellow and slightly sooty flame. It was dextrorotatory $[\alpha]_D = +33.4$ in alcoholic solution. (Found: C, 61.6 ; 61.72 ; H, 8.5; 8.6 per cent. M. W. cryoscopic in glacial acetic acid, 423, 427 and in phenol 435, 439. $C_{22}H_{36}O_8$ requires C, 61.68; H, 8.41 per cent. M. W. 428.)

The mother-liquor from which corchorin was separated was concentrated to a syrup. It gave no precipitate with potassium-mercuric iodide, iodine or phosphomolybdic acid thus showing the absence of any substance of alkaloidal nature.

With the object of ascertaining whether any definite hydrolytic product could be obtained from the substance, the syrup was heated for some time with moderately strong hydrochloric acid when a dark brown solid soon began to separate. After hydrolysis was complete the mixture was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was first washed with aqueous sodium hydroxide to remove some colouring matter and subsequently with water, after which it was dried and the ether removed when a small quantity of a yellow solid remained. This was purified from alcohol when it melted at 114-115°. It was found to be the hydrolytic product of the glucoside corchorin and further work to elucidate its composition is in progress.

The syrup contained an abundance of sugar and in order to confirm the identity of the sugar a portion of the syrup was treated with ammoniacal lead acetate which gave a voluminous precipitate. On heating it assumed a salmon-pink colour. This was filtered,

washed with water, suspended in water and decomposed by sulphuretted hydrogen and filtered. The filtrate was carefully neutralised by sodium carbonate and clarified by animal charcoal. The filtrate readily reduced Fehling's solution and yielded *d*-phenylglucosazone, m. p. 203°, and this showed the presence of glucose in the seeds.

The Resin (B).

The black resinous material contained in the portion of the alcoholic extract, which had been separated from the aqueous liquid as above described was digested with alcohol, mixed with purified powdered pumice stone and the thoroughly dried mixture was extracted successively in a Soxhlet's apparatus with various solvents. Only chloroform and ethyl acetate extracts yielded crystalline substances.

Chloroform Extract of the Resin.—This extract was a dark brown solid, which was again dissolved in boiling chloroform and on slow evaporation of the solution a crystalline mass separated out which on further purification from alcohol yielded a colourless mass, m.p. 172-174° which was found to be identical with corchorin (*loc. cit.*).

Ethyl Acetate Extract of the Resin.—This extract was a deep brown solid, and on slow evaporation of the concentrated solution of the extract beautiful clusters of stout, rhombic, brown plates deposited. When powdered it was found to be brittle and white inside. When heated on the platinum foil it burnt with a sooty flame leaving no residue. It melted at 165-168° and was sparingly soluble in water and alcohol but readily soluble in nitrobenzene, methyl alcohol and pyridine. With concentrated sulphuric acid it gave a deep red colouration but no colouration with ferric chloride. Its aqueous solution was neutral to litmus and at first had an astringent taste but soon developed an after-bitter taste. As the substance obtained was very small it could not be analysed.

Effect of Corchorin on Red Blood Corpuscles.—The object of this experiment was to see whether the jute-seed bitter had any hemolytic action on red blood corpuscles. In the present experiment fresh and washed human corpuscles completely freed from serum by repeated centrifuging with normal saline was used. The red blood corpuscles were suspended in physiological saline. 2 C.c. of the suspended red blood corpuscles were taken in a test-tube and mixed

with a known amount of corchorin in a known volume of normal saline so that the combined volume was brought to a standard volume of 10 c.c. The contents of the two tubes were rapidly mixed three times and then allowed to rest first in a stand at the laboratory temperature and then in an incubator at 37°. For comparison a standard hemolysed tube prepared by adding a known amount of saponin in normal saline was used.

R.B.C.=2 c.c. Total volume=10 c.c.

Corchorin 0.1% in c.c.	0	0.5	1.0	2.0
Time.				
0	No effect.	No effect.	No effect.	No effect.
15 min.	"	Slight ppt.	Slight ppt.	Slight ppt.
30 "	"	"	"	"
60 "	"	"	"	"
After 24 hours at 37°	Settles.	Completely settles.	Completely settles.	Completely settles.

The above result showed that corchorin was devoid of any hemolytic action on red blood corpuscles.

Bactericidal Action on B.Coli.—A fresh 24 hours culture of *B. coli* was kept suspended in a sterilised saturated solution of corchorin in normal saline. After 25 minutes, a drop of suspension was put in a fresh agar tube. After 24 hours *B.Coli* was seen to grow in the tube. This shows that the saturated solution of corchorin had no bactericidal effect on *B.Coli*.

The jute-seed oil and the bitter principle are now being submitted to further physiological tests.

Summary.

A more extensive investigation of the jute seeds has been undertaken. Preliminary examination shows that the seeds are rich in phosphates and potash. Water extracts 3.4 per cent. of a crude nitrogenous substance which has been found to contain the enzyme catalase.

The general character of the seeds has been determined by extracting the seeds with various solvents.

The petroleum extract which amounted to 14.72% of the whole contain a fatty oil, a detailed account of which has been given in Part II.

The ether extract amounted to 1.36% of the whole and consists of some fatty matter probably lecithin and a colourless microcrystalline mass possessing phenolic properties.

The chloroform extract amounted to 1.9% and consists of brown resin from which nothing definite has been isolated.

The alcoholic extract which amounted to 15.72% is the more important product obtained from jute seeds and special consideration has therefore been given to the character of the product in the present investigation.

Raffinose has been obtained from this extract to the extent of about 3 per cent. thus confirming the observation of Annett.

Corchorin, ($C_{22}H_{36}O_8$) the active principle of the seeds has been isolated in a very pure form. It is a glucoside having an extremely bitter taste "ten times more bitter than quinine sulphate". It forms glistening rhombic prisms melting at 174-175° and has saponin-like properties but unlike saponin it has no hemolytic action on red blood corpuscles. It is dextrorotatory and the combustion and molecular weight determination indicate a cyclic alcohol. Further physical and chemical properties are being studied with a view to determine its constitution.

The alcoholic extract also yields two other products, one crystalline and another amorphous which have not yet been characterised.

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